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Gastronomy Museums as an Element Bringing Forgotten Values to Light: A Proposal for Sinop Province

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this research is to measure the gastronomy tourism potential of the province for the proposal of a gastronomy museum in Sinop. The sub-objectives of the research include designing a gastronomy museum specific to Sinop, determining the strengths of the gastronomy potential of the province, and ensuring that this potential is included among the gastronomy tour routes. At the same time, it is aimed to provide a perspective on the importance of opening a gastronomy museum in the city in terms of the sustainability of gastronomic values in Sinop. In this context, the study analyzes the gastronomic values of Sinop and how these values can be made sustainable. Within the scope of the research, the content analysis technique was used as a data collection method. The gastronomic richness of Sinop and the contribution of these richnesses to tourism potential were evaluated. In this way, it is aimed at developing strategies to increase the attractiveness of the province in terms of gastronomy tourism. As a result of these analyses, Sinop's unique gastronomic richnesses and their contributions to tourism potential have been comprehensively evaluated. At the end of the study, strategies have been developed to increase the attractiveness of Sinop in terms of gastronomy tourism and to support sustainable tourism development. Suggestions include organizing local cuisine festivals, creating interactive and educational exhibitions within the gastronomy museum, branding local products, and increasing promotional

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activities. In addition, raising awareness and training local people and businesses about gastronomy and tourism are also among the suggestions. These strategies aim to maximize the gastronomy tourism potential of Sinop and contribute to the economic and cultural development of the province.

1. Introduction

With the development of elements such as technology, industry, and agriculture, changes have also occurred in people's habits. With the globalizing world, many sectors have been affected by this change. The tourism sector has also been affected by this globalization in line with people's desire to discover new places, sightseeing, and eating and drinking (Kozak et al., 2017). While people carry out tourism mobility, especially on the basis of the sea, sand, and sun, in order to take a break from their busy work tempo, changes have also occurred in these habits with the globalizing world, and alternative tourism types have emerged. One of these alternative tourism types is gastronomy tourism, which has gained popularity especially in the 21st century. Gastronomy tourism has come to the forefront with its attraction elements such as the culinary culture of a region or region, tours to examine local dishes, gastronomy festivals, and gastronomy museums. Within the scope of gastronomy tourism, many studies have been carried out in the literature, but it has been determined that there are not enough studies on gastronomy museums. In this study, some gastronomy museums operating in the world and in Turkey are mentioned. It has been determined that gastronomy museums operate in different themes. Considering Turkey's culinary culture, it is seen that the tourism sector and the academic field are of great importance. Considering the gastronomy potential of many different provinces from different geographies, it is thought to make significant contributions to the tourism sector. For this reason, the main purpose of this research is to introduce the culinary culture of Sinop province of gastronomy tourism, which will make significant contributions to the tourism sector, and to present a proposal for the opening of a gastronomy museum in the city in question.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Gastronomy tourism and destination marketing

Food is one of the basic necessities that individuals perform in order to sustain their lives and survive at the same time. However, in addition to basic necessity, the concept of food is also one of the leading roles of regional culture and identity (Quan et al., 2004). In the historical process, when people migrated for

various reasons in order to determine their living areas, culinary cultures were shaped (Düzgün & Durlu Özkaya, 2015). Gastronomy is a concept that reflects the food and beverage cultures of societies. It is stated that the concept of gastronomy is a concept that is becoming more important day by day and makes important contributions to the region (Selwood, 2003). The concept of gastronomy is also defined as the art of gourmet and good eating and the science of good food and beverage (Herbst et al., 2007). Another definition of the concept of gastronomy is “the accumulation of knowledge on every subject covering human life quality and nutrition” (Baysal et al., 2009).

Gastronomy tourism comes to the forefront in the use of its values as an attraction factor. People visit regions to experience food and beverage elements that they have not experienced before and to discover them due to their interest in different culinary cultures, and visit the producers, restaurants, festivals, and gastronomy museums (Long, 2003; Harrington et al., 2010; Yüncü, 2010). Special interest tourism is a type of tourism that individuals realize for their interests. Gastronomy tourism is also a type of tourism considered within the scope of special interest tourism (Tanrısevdi et al., 2003). Gastronomy tourism, which is considered within the scope of special interest tourism, has become a prominent type of tourism, especially in the 21st century (Aksoy et al., 2015). Destination is the name given to a country, city, or geographical region. This concept is one that varies according to people's reasons for traveling, their level of education, and the results of their experiences as a result of traveling (Buharis, 2000).

With the increase in visits in tourism with technological developments, each destination is in competition to improve its own image. This competition causes the intangible cultural heritage of the destination in question to become even more important (UNWTO, 2021). It is stated that a product or region must have attractiveness in order to integrate with the tourism sector and generate income. How and how this attractiveness will be marketed in tourism is one of the important issues that need to be known. It is stated that attractions will make significant contributions to the region by attracting the attention of visitors in tourism. In tourism, there are 4 concepts that are effective in making a product or destination attractive. These concepts are socio-cultural, economic, natural, and psychological elements (Kozak et al., 2017).

2.2. Examples of gastronomy museums

With the demand and development of gastronomy tourism, researchers from many different countries have recently taken part in various studies within the scope

of the tourism in question. Based on these studies, it is mentioned that Italy, France, and Spain are the countries that receive the most visitors under the title of gastronomy tourism in the 21st century. It is stated that these countries, which host gastronomy tourism, host visitors with their rich and valuable culinary cultures as well as their historical, natural, and cultural beauty and values (Öner, 2018; Belpınar, 2014). When Turkey is analyzed in terms of tourism, it is stated as one of the leading countries with its cultural heritage, natural beauties, culinary culture, historical background, and tourist attraction elements. In terms of culinary culture, Hatay, Şanlıurfa, Mardin, Mersin, and Adana provinces are stated as the leading provinces with their famous flavors through gastronomy tourism and have a great share in destination preference (Güzel Şahin et al., 2015).

2.2.1. World examples

It is stated that gastronomy museums, whose value is increasing within the scope of gastronomy tourism, have an important place in order to increase the attractiveness of the destination to be traveled (Demirci, 2021). Gastronomy museums are a route included in the visits of many local and foreign tourists. It can be defined as an area where those values are exhibited by bringing the culinary culture and forgotten foods to the surface (Sarı Gök et al., 2021).

The museum of cheese products includes free cheese tasting, various types of cheese, preparation of cheeses, and the and the history of cheese making. The cheese museum in the Netherlands is one of the best examples (Amsterdam Cheese Museum, 2024). In chocolate museums, visitors can taste many types of chocolate, such as hot, cold, white, bitter, sweet, solid, liquid, as well as hot, cold, white, bitter, bitter, sweet, sweet, solid, liquid, etc. (Girak, 2014). One of the leading chocolate museums is the Schokoladenmuseum Köln in Germany, which is becoming the center of attention of visitors (Schokoladenmuseum Köln, 2024). In olive-olive oil museums, the process of making, preparation techniques, and consumption of olive oil since ancient times are conveyed (Arıkan Saltık, 2017). Sparta Olive and Olive Oil Museum in Greece is one of the most important examples. It describes the stages of olive oil integration with cultural values since prehistoric times. The museum includes information boards on the use of olive oil by the Greek society (Gür, 2017).

Culinary culture museums are museums that help to introduce the local cuisine cultures of countries and regions. In the museum, many elements, such as tools used in the production of local dishes, wax sculptures, and tasting festivals, are exhibited. The Greek Gastronomy Museum, located in Athens, the capital of Greece, is one of the best examples of culinary culture museums and has been operating since

2014. In wine museums, vineyards, viticulture, tasting events, stages of wine production, and regional wine tastings take place. In this way, the wine history, culture, and promotion of the region in question are realized (Inácio, 2018).

2.2.2. Examples from Turkey

Kutman Wine Museum in Tekirdağ is one of the important examples. In this museum, the machines, tools, and documents that Adnan Kutman collected about wine for about 15 years have been exhibited in the exhibition area since 2003 (Kutman, 2024). Another example is the Emine Göğüş Culinary Museum in Gaziantep. It is the first culinary culture museum established in Turkey. According to the study conducted by Dere Yağar (2012), the museum presents the cultural atmosphere of the province in question, the process of making the yuvarlama dish, which is unique to the region, sausage, walnut, and bastık. The tricks to be considered in the making and cooking of Mırza coffee, which is famous for Gaziantep, are conveyed by mannequins dressed in local clothes. In addition to these, the tools and equipment used by the city, which is rich in food and beverage culture, while realizing these elements are exhibited. In addition to these, there are soaps produced from olives and oil (Adatepe, 2024). In Hatay province, the Museum of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants is the first and only museum in Turkey in this field and was established with the increasing demand for botanical and health tourism, one of the alternative tourism types. The museum has been operating since 2012 and aims to exhibit this valuable and endemic plant diversity and the sustainability of plants (Gökçe et al., 2017).

3. Methodology

The main purpose of this study is to bring to light the forgotten gastronomic elements of Sinop province and to present a proposal for the opening of a gastronomy museum in the said province. In this study, the document analysis technique, one of the qualitative research methods, was used. Yıldırım et al. (2008) defined qualitative research method as a qualitative process carried out by using qualitative data collection analyses such as document analysis, observation, and interview without ignoring the realism of the information obtained. At the same time, the qualitative research method seeks answers by examining some different social fields and the communities that make up these fields (Berg et al., 2019). For this reason, a semi-structured interview was conducted with an official working in the Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism.

4. Results and Discussion

Sinop province is defined as a province that has hosted many cultures over the centuries. Culinary culture has been shaped and maintained with societies migrating from different regions. Sinop has also been an important fishing center throughout history due to its coastal location. In the villages of Sinop, small-scale products are produced at home, but it is stated that they are not offered to the tourism market. These products are prepared organically in homes and offered to buyers in the village market (İpar et al., 2014). According to Yurt et al. (2022), it is emphasized that the diversity of local products has increased due to the rainfall due to the location of the province. As a result of the research, it was stated that there are products that are suitable for health and, at the same time, preserve their freshness throughout the region. It is stated that various herbs and vegetables grown in nature are frequently used in Sinop province (Genç et al., 2019) and that it has an important place in the use of fishery and seafood (Tırıl et al., 2017) by hosting the only natural harbor of the Black Sea. Sinop also has a rich biodiversity, and the tree species in the region are linden, oak, plane, pine, rooster, beech, hornbeam, chestnut, and poplar (Sinop Governorship, 2024). With the initiative initiated under the leadership of Sinop University, Sinop chestnut honey received a geographical indication certificate and gained brand value with the name SINATE, which was formed by abbreviating the names of Sinop, Ayancık, Türkeli, and Erfelek (Sinop University, 2024).

4.1. Gastronomic values of Sinop

4.1.1. Sinop keşkeği

In Sinop, traditional ceremonial keşkek is cooked on celebrations and special occasions. Although the production of keşkek in Sinop is similar to other regions in Turkey, it has been observed that the recipe has been differentiated with the use of unique ingredients with the mission of symbolizing abundance. When the culinary culture of Sinop was analyzed, it was found that there are many different recipes of keshkek. It has been determined that it takes place on the tables during Hıdırellez celebrations, weddings and circumcision weddings, religious holidays, soldier farewells, dental wheat for babies, and religious holidays (Ademoğlu & Durlu Özkaya, 2021).

It is said that during Hıdırellez celebrations, it is cooked by locals with prayers to wish fertility with additions such as chicken, meat, beans, and corn (Çek, 2022). For the development of tourism in Sinop, it has been emphasized that the tourism potential of the city will develop by keeping the culinary culture alive, introducing it to visitors, and considering its sustainability (Met, 2012).

4.1.2. Sinop mantisi

Mantı is defined as a valuable food that is formed by adding various products to the dough and is widely known in many countries. It is a traditional Turkish dish that is preferred by large masses and is a feast of flavor in the combination of dough and meat. It is stated that mantı, which is also combined with potatoes and cheese, is formed by bending and closing in rectangular and other shapes (Güler et al., 2020).

It is said that Sinop manti is one of the most favorite products of Sinop province that has received a geographical sign. Although its name has not been in vogue in the past years, today it takes its place as a very important product in terms of gastronomy tourism. Sinop ravioli is also pronounced as “ear dough” by the local people. It is said that its name comes from the way it is folded. It is emphasized that Sinop ravioli is preferred not only because of its folding shape but also because of the flavor and abundance of the filling. It is said that in the past years, meat was used in the filling, not minced meat. (Seçkin Sevinc, 2021) It is stated that Sinop ravioli is served with yogurt in half and walnuts roasted in butter in the other half after the ravioli is placed on the plate (Lezzet, 2021).

4.1.3. Sinop lakerdasi

Both in ancient times and today, with the arrival of spring in the Black Sea region, fish are frequently seen in the seas until the weather gets cold. The main source of livelihood in the Black Sea region has always been fish products (Aylak Lakerda, 2020). One of the oldest fish preservation methods was determined as the salting method. It is divided into two as dry salting and wet salting according to the size of the fish (Turan et al., 2006).

The history of Sinop Laker is based on a very long history. It has a very important place in the economic development of Sinop province. Sinop lakerdasi is desalinated in a salting container before it is offered for sale. After vacuum packaging, an amount of vegetable oil is poured over it. Before it is consumed, it is desalinated by soaking in water. (Turkish Patent Office, 2023)

4.1.4. Sinop nokulu

Sinop nokulu was taken under protection as of 25.04.2011 and registered by Sinop Chamber of Commerce and Industry on 15.17.2017. Sinop nokul is a type of pastry belonging to Sinop. The filling is made with minced meat, walnuts, and grapes. It is said that Sinop nokul was served only on the eve and feast days in the past years and was also served to the guests coming home. Today, it is frequently

produced in bakeries and patisseries in Sinop province and attracts the attention of tourists. (Turkish Patent Office, 2017)

4.1.5. Boyabat sirik kebabi

Sirik kebab is seen as an ancestral tradition. It is generally described as a dish that shepherds see from their fathers and grandfathers and pass on to generations. Sirik kebab is not a type of kebab that can be cooked in ordinary cookers. It gets its name come a tradition, especially in Boyabat and Saraydüzü, the districts of Sinop province (Akyol, 2018).

Boyabat sirik kebab was taken under protection on 21.05.2018 and officially registered on 28.09.2020. Boyabat sirik kebab is also known as *bandit kebab*. It has been made in this region for many years with Karayaka breed sheep, provided that it is at least 6 months old. The reason why this type of sheep is preferred is that it has a meat rich in fiber. (Turkish Patent Office, 2020)

4.2. Tools and equipment used in Sinop cuisine

The most important components of the food and beverage culture are the tools used to present the dishes. The tools and equipment in question are said to be a material element that has been shaped over time by trial and error. It is stated that people from the past to the present use these tools and equipment in order to continue their lives and to facilitate their work. These tools and equipment have changed from society to society in the past and have been shaped differently from geography to geography. When evaluated within the scope of Sinop province, the raw material of the materials was obtained from wood due to the physical conditions of the region. The tree species that are the raw materials of the tools used in the construction of the materials in the said province are ash, linden, boxwood, beech, fir, chestnut, and pine trees. The reason why these tree species are preferred is that the raw material used is water-resistant, knotless, soft, easy to process, light in weight, and fragrant. Accordingly, wooden cups, water storage bins, and jugs are made from fir wood because they emit a good odor; tables and dough troughs are produced from ash wood because of their hardness; rolling pins are made from linden and beech woods because of their flat, knotless, and soft structures; and mourning trees and dough shovels are produced from pine, chestnut, and fir woods because of their water-resistant properties (Acar, 2023).

Table 1. Tools and equipment used in Sinop cuisine

Tools and equipment used in Sinop cuisine	Purpose the equipment is used for
Aşurma	Large copper saucepan
Bardak	Water jug made of pine
Barmaklu Gaşuk	Fork
Bişek	Churn hammer
Bocuk	Small, round, stemless, pine or earthenware jug
Bocut	Small water jug made of pine wood
Bodaç	Small jug made of pine wood or earthenware, round, handle-less jug
Bodiri	Small earthenware water jug with pitcher and handle
Büşürgeç	Flat shovel used for turning bread and phyllo dough on a aking tray
Caba	Casserole, clay pot, earthenware pot
Capcak	Scoop-shaped tree on the sides of a fountain or well, mashpot
Cere	Soil testing
Çevirgeç	Wooden shovel for turning phyllo dough on an baking sheet
Çöven	Earthen pot with popcorn in it
Depme	Narrow-mouthed water jug
Dımbıl	Small churn made of wood
Dutak	Pot holder
Ergüç	Churn handle, knocker
Ersün	Flat iron tool for scraping or cutting dry dough stuck to the dough trough
Evcük	Churn hammer
Fişek	Churn hammer
Gesuç	Wooden tool for turning bread on a baking sheet
Gönce	Table cloth made of tanned leather
Gözer	Large sieve for sieving wheat, soil, etc.
Guvan	Churn
Güdü	Water jerry can made of wood
Hebene	Testing
Hereni	Cookware
Kadif	Tray
Kaşıklık	Spoon basket made of wood
Kebene	Water jug
Kecik	Handles, handles of boiler or saucepan
Keküç	Shovel for turning the bread cooked on a baking sheet
Kendürük	Tablecloth
Kersen	Wooden vessel in which dough is kneaded

Kesgüç	Flat wooden paddle for turning the bread on the hair
Keşüt	Flat wooden shovel for turning bread on a baking sheet
Medine	Small cupboards, without doors, on the kitchen walls, near the hobs
Oklaç	Rolling pin
Örsün	Iron tool for scraping the dough board
Senek	Water container carved out of pine wood, wooden jug
Sergen	Kitchen shelf
Sergi	Table cloth
Sırca	Porcelain plate
Silgüç	Dishcloth
Sini	Copper tray, tableware
Söngüye	A pole with a rag at the end for sweeping the oven
Sürgüç	Dishcloth, rags
Şapşak	Wood carved bowl cup
Şapşalak	Wooden mugs used for drinking water from a spring
Şarapkana	A tool for squeezing the juice of fruits such as grapes and apples
Tehne	Dishcloth
Tendil	Cookware
Tengere	Cookware
Test	Large basin
Tuluk	Water jerry can
Yassıağaç	Board on which dough is rolled out and food is eaten
Yayev	Tablecloth
Zöngce	Oven shovel

Source: Acar (2023)

Table 2. Usability of the elements in culinary museums in Sinop cuisine

Elements in culinary museums	Availability in Sinop province
Geographically marked products, dishes	There are 12 pieces
Information boards	May take place
Tools and equipment used since the past	It is included in Table 1 above
Mannequins showing the cooking process	May take place
Showcases	May take place
Exhibition of motifs of gastronomy products	May take place
Cooking, tasting and recipe section of local specialities	It can also be implemented in order to increase welfare through the local community
Restaurant department	May be of interest to incoming tourists
Museum logo	In the introduction
Souvenir department	May be favoured by visitors

Gastronomy library	Available from the local authorities
Chronological order of food culture history and standard recipes	Available from local people, authorities and academics in the region

Source: Bilir (2022)

When the sections of culinary museums are examined from a general point of view, it can be said that the opening of a gastronomy museum in Sinop is an ordinary situation due to the fact that Sinop province has a very rich gastronomic location. Based on the above-mentioned elements and with research from the sources, it has been evaluated that a section where the tools used in gastronomy museums are exhibited, a section where the tools used in gastronomy museums are exhibited, animations and showcase sections symbolizing the local people describing the production stages of local dishes animated with mannequins, and a museum house with information boards can be an important step in terms of significantly increasing the gastronomy tourism potential of Sinop province and ensuring the welfare of the local people, and at the same time, in the recognition of local dishes, Sinop local dishes can be an important step in terms of including more products among geographically marked products. The interview held at Sinop Provincial Directorate is given in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Interview questions and answers

First of all, we are working on opening a gastronomy museum in Sinop Province. Do you have any studies/projects in this regard?	“No project/study has been done for this yet, but it seems to me a very logical and beautiful project.”
What are your views on opening a gastronomy museum in Sinop province?	“I mean, gastronomy is a very detailed subject, and it is a very different innovation in Sinop. In some districts, especially herbs are very prominent, while in some districts, for example, there is more diversity in Sinop, especially in this kebab. We have done a lot of work on gastronomy. For example, we are organizing a Turkish cuisine week. At this stage, we are doing good work to present all of them, to make people taste and promote them. However, we had never thought of a project within the scope of museology. It is a good subject in terms of its feasibility.”
Do you think a gastronomy museum can take place in Sinop? If it can take place, which elements can it contain?	“Yes, it can be, it can be, but there are not many elements that we are assertive about gastronomy like the provinces in the east. Fish can be at the forefront in this regard. If more emphasis is

	given to this subject, we have actually come a long way in fish. Even ravioli has started to be made from fish. I think that if a very deep study is done at this stage, very good things can emerge.”
Can the opening of such a museum in Sinop province lead to an increase in the tourism activity of the province?	“I think it can happen, I think it can get people's attention.”

Source: Authors' elaboration

When the findings obtained from the interview in Table 3 are examined, it is possible to say that the gastronomy potential of Sinop province is high. For this reason, the fact that there has not been any project related to the gastronomy museum before emphasizes the importance of the study. It is said that gastronomy tourism is a fairly new phenomenon in Sinop. The place of the gastronomy museum is important in the cultural transfer of the province in question and, at the same time, in bringing the forgotten gastronomic items to light. Considering that gastronomy tourism is developing day by day, it is thought that although Sinop province has this potential, its flavors are not sufficiently recognized. In order to ensure the sustainability and recognition of local flavors, the establishment of a gastronomy museum in Sinop will ensure both the development of the city and the transfer of its values to future generations.

5. Conclusion

Museums play an important role in preserving and transferring cultural values from the past to the future. In many countries around the world, gastronomic values and culinary cultures are preserved and exhibited in museums. Gastronomy museums aim to preserve and transfer local dishes, which are cultural values and stand out in gastronomy, to future generations. Gastronomy museums also positively affect the destination image of the regions where they are located (Sandıkçı et al., 2019; Can et al., 2019). Therefore, gastronomy museums have a special importance in introducing and exhibiting the regional cuisine and revealing the recipes and tools that are about to be forgotten. Sinop is a province that stands out with its nature, culture, and gastronomy. Sinop has been home to many civilizations from the past to the present. Each of the civilizations that lived in the province in question has both shaped and developed the culinary culture and added beauty to the city, which is valued and famous for its ports.

Each of the civilizations that came and settled in different regions created a culinary culture in Sinop by reflecting their own culture. Over time, this culinary

culture has developed and expanded, and the local foods we see within the scope of today's Sinop flavors have emerged. Among these foods, there are also products registered with geographical indication. Sinop is a province that stands out with its natural attractions in terms of tourism. For this reason, in this study, aims to create awareness among the tourists who come for tourism mobility to taste local foods and the local people to transfer these local foods to future generations. The food culture of a region helps to understand the culture of that region. For this reason, it is possible to understand the lifestyles of provinces that are famous for a dish from their food culture. Visitors prefer to eat a dish on site in the atmosphere of that region. In this way, not tasting a local dish in the city where it is owned will give tourists a more unforgettable experience. This situation will also be very important for the welfare of local people and tourism stakeholders. According to the information obtained as a result of the research, it is determined that if a gastronomy museum is opened in Sinop, the welfare and tourism potential of the province in question will increase significantly. Some recommendations have been determined within the framework of all the results obtained. At the beginning of these recommendations, it is determined that it is necessary to open a gastronomy museum in Sinop in order to ensure the sustainability of the culinary culture of Sinop by protecting it, promoting these values nationally and internationally, not forgetting the kitchen utensils used in the kitchens from the past to the present, to increase the number of visitors coming to Sinop for tourism purposes, and to ensure the welfare of the city. Tourism stakeholders and local people in the province should be aware of the gastronomic potential and play an active role in promoting these flavors and values. In this framework, new plans should be realized with the increase in tourism mobility. Booklets with local flavors should be given to incoming visitors, and visitors should be made aware of this. With the positive feedback received, literature should be included in the literature for the opening of a gastronomy museum. It is recommended that the studies to be carried out in the province in question be carried out on the basis of all districts and villages. Care should be taken not to exceed the environmental, social, and psychological carrying capacity of the city during the increase in visitors. Tourism stakeholders in Sinop province should be included in the studies, and procedures for opening a gastronomy museum should be started. Considering the gastronomic values in Sinop, national and even international gastronomy museums should be examined, and plans should be started.

It is suggested that the gastronomy museum to be opened should include a restaurant section, a tasting section for local products, and a gastronomy library. At the same time, courses should be opened for local dishes of the region in order to

encourage local people. It would be more efficient for visitors to visit the museum with a guide. In the tasting section inside the museum, they should be encouraged to participate in the production stages with local clothes. Since Sinop is a province rich in fish diversity, fish can be exhibited in a section of the museum. Before starting to work on the opening of the gastronomy museum, gastronomy museums in Turkey and even abroad, if possible, should be visited and examined, and a planning scheme should emerge. This will help to make a museum plan by experiencing the atmosphere one-on-one and taking inspiration. In order to show visitors the existence of gastronomy museums and raise awareness, travel agencies can include visits to domestic and international gastronomy museums in their tour programs. In order for Sinop to develop gastronomy tourism, local people, tourism stakeholders, and academicians in the region should support the opening of a gastronomy museum. This group will play an important role in the opening of the museum. Deficiencies in advertising and promotion should be eliminated in terms of the recognition of the gastronomy museum. It would be useful to take the initiative to open gastronomy museums in provinces that do not have a gastronomy museum in Turkey. With the increasing access to and use of the internet in the globalizing world, creating a web page for the proposed gastronomy museum may contribute. By conducting academic studies and developing joint projects with universities, gastronomy museums can become not only a tourist attraction for the promotion of gastronomy culture but also an institute as a learning place, especially for students studying gastronomy and culinary arts. Future studies can investigate how gastronomy museums contribute to the region and the public.

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